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ECONOMIC OPPORTUNITIES FOR INCREASING EMPLOYMENT THROUGH THE DEVELOPMENT OF SMALL BUSINESS ENTITIES IN KHOREZM REGION

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Abstract: This article analyzes the economic opportunities for increasing employment in Khorezm region through the development of small business entities on a scientific-theoretical and statistical basis. At the same time, it demonstrates the need not only to increase the number of jobs in small business, but also to strengthen their sustainability, formal status, profitability, and capacity to generate high added value.

Keywords: small business, private entrepreneurship, employment, Khorezm region, regional economy, labor market, economic opportunities, entrepreneurial potential, formal jobs.

Аннотация: В данной статье на научно-теоретической и статистической основе анализируются экономические возможности повышения занятости населения Хорезмской области посредством развития субъектов малого бизнеса. Вместе с тем обосновывается необходимость не только увеличения количества рабочих мест в секторе малого бизнеса, но и повышения их устойчивости, формального статуса, прибыльности и способности создавать высокую добавленную стоимость.

Ключевые слова: малый бизнес, частное предпринимательство, занятость, Хорезмская область, региональная экономика, рынок труда, экономические возможности, предпринимательский потенциал, формальные рабочие места.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada Xorazm viloyatida kichik biznes subyektlarini rivojlantirish orqali aholi bandligini oshirishning iqtisodiy imkoniyatlari ilmiy-nazariy va statistik asosda tahlil qilingan. Shu bilan birga, kichik biznes sohasida nafaqat ish o'rinlari sonini ko'paytirish, balki ularning barqarorligi, rasmiy maqomi, rentabelligi hamda yuqori qo'shilgan qiymat yaratish salohiyatini mustahkamlash zarurligi asoslab berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: kichik biznes, xususiy tadbirkorlik, bandlik, Xorazm viloyati, mintaqaviy iqtisodiyot, mehnat bozori, iqtisodiy imkoniyatlar, tadbirkorlik salohiyati, rasmiy ish o'rinlari.

INTRODUCTION

In the current context, the sustainability of regional economic development is determined primarily by ensuring employment and using labor resources effectively. Small business entities are an important source of increasing regional employment because they can quickly adapt to the labor market, organize types of activity that require relatively little capital, expand self-employment, and support family entrepreneurship. This issue is especially relevant for Khorezm region, where the population is relatively dense and the potential of services, agriculture, tourism, and handicrafts is high.

The relevance of the article lies in the fact that, although small business has a large share in ensuring employment in Khorezm region, the quality and sustainability of the jobs created in this sector continue to improve and offer broad opportunities for further research. The concentration of many small entities in trade and small-scale service segments, expanding access to finance and markets, the growing resilience of new businesses, and the increasing utilization of opportunities for youth and women's entrepreneurship enhance the impact of small business on employment.

The purpose of the study is to identify the economic opportunities for increasing employment in Khorezm region through the development of small business entities and to develop scientific and practical proposals for implementing these opportunities in practice.

The scientific novelty of the study is that the relationship between small business and employment is assessed not only through the number of entities or the total number of employed people, but also from the

perspectives of “employment capacity,” “survival,” “sectoral specialization,” and “the result of creating formal jobs.” On this basis, a specific model linking small business with labor market policy is proposed for Khorezm region.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

The role of small business and entrepreneurship in economic development was initially explained through classical innovation-based approaches. J. Schumpeter interprets the entrepreneur as an entity that carries out “new combinations” in the economy, that is, introduces new products, new markets, new technologies, and new methods of organization. This approach is also important for Khorezm region, because in the region small business should be developed not merely by increasing the number of trade entities, but by expanding agro-processing, tourism services, digital services, and handicrafts on an innovative basis [1].

D. Birch evaluated small and new enterprises as the main source of job creation. Although his research gave strong impetus to subsequent studies on small business, later literature emphasized that not only firm size, but also firm age, market-entry conditions, and growth capacity determine employment outcomes [2]. D. Storey shows that not all small businesses become fast-growing entities; rather, small firms that have a major impact on employment usually form a limited group with high growth potential. This means that, in Khorezm as well, instead of mass lending to small business, selective support should be directed toward sectors with high employment capacity [3].

T. Beck, A. Demirgüç-Kunt, and R. Levine demonstrated a relationship between the share of small and medium-sized businesses and economic growth and poverty reduction, while emphasizing that the institutional environment, the financial system, and competitive conditions play an important role in strengthening this relationship. Therefore, an increase in the number of small business entities does not by itself guarantee high efficiency; they must be connected with finance, infrastructure, markets, and a skills system [4].

In their study covering 99 countries, M. Ayyagari, A. Demirgüç-Kunt, and V. Maksimovic substantiated that small and especially young firms play an important role in employment and job creation. J. Haltiwanger, R. Jarmin, and J. Miranda show that the factor of “young firms” is stronger than “small firms” in the job-creation process. This conclusion provides an important scientific basis for Khorezm region: monitoring newly established small business entities during the first 24 months and providing them with financial, accounting, marketing, and market-entry assistance strengthens employment outcomes [5] [6].

The World Bank regards small and medium-sized enterprises as the backbone of most economies, noting that globally they account for around 90 percent of businesses and more than half of employment. The International Labour Organization indicates that MSMEs cover approximately 70 percent of global employment, but many of them face problems associated with low productivity, informality, and weak working conditions. Based on this approach, in developing small business in Khorezm region, the main criterion should be not merely “job creation,” but the creation of “decent and sustainable jobs” [7] [8].

The OECD report on Uzbekistan’s business climate identifies access to finance, the competitive environment, infrastructure, and digital skills as important factors in private sector development. The World Bank report on youth employment in Uzbekistan notes that low wages and weak labor demand are among the key constraints to youth employment. The UNDP study on women’s entrepreneurship emphasizes the importance of financial services, business incubators, digital platforms, childcare infrastructure, and sectoral approaches in developing women’s entrepreneurship [9] [10] [11].

International studies extensively cover the impact of small business, young firms, and financial opportunities on employment, while reports on Uzbekistan consider the business environment and employment issues at a general level. However, in the case of Khorezm region, the impact of small business entities on employment has not been studied in sufficient depth in relation to sectoral structure, the structure of gross regional product (GRP), formal jobs, and the survival of new businesses. This article is aimed precisely at filling that gap.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study used comparative-statistical analysis, time-series analysis, structural analysis, scientific generalization, and economic comparison methods. For the empirical analysis, open data from the Integrated Statistical Information System (SIAT) of the National Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan were used as a basis, including the number of people employed in small entrepreneurship entities in Khorezm region, the number of operating small entrepreneurship entities, the unemployment rate, and data on gross regional product for January-December 2025.

The dynamics of employment in small entrepreneurship for 2018-2024 and the GRP structure for the end of 2025 were selected as the analysis period. This approach, on the one hand, shows changes in the labor

market and, on the other hand, makes it possible to determine through which sectors small business can be expanded.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

According to SIAT data, the number of people employed in small entrepreneurship entities in Khorezm region amounted to 573.4 thousand in 2018, 591.9 thousand in 2019, 567.9 thousand in 2020, 574.3 thousand in 2021, 579.3 thousand in 2022, 609.8 thousand in 2023, and 621.0 thousand in 2024. Although the indicator declined in 2020 under the impact of the pandemic, a recovery and growth trend was observed in subsequent years [12].

The unemployment rate in Khorezm region was 10.9 percent in 2020, while it declined to 5.4 percent in 2024 and, according to preliminary data, to 4.7 percent in 2025. This decline is associated with employment policy, support for entrepreneurship, and the recovery of economic activity. However, a decline in unemployment does not mean that all jobs created in small business are sustainable and high-paying. Therefore, the main attention should be focused on the qualitative indicators of employment [13].

The number of operating small entrepreneurship entities in Khorezm region was 15,453 in 2020, 18,875 in 2021, 21,984 in 2022, 25,616 in 2023, 23,854 in 2024, 20,528 in 2025, and 23,465 as of January 1, 2026. This dynamic shows that the small business environment is active, but the decline in 2024-2025 may be associated with the suspension of activity by some entities or re-registration processes. This, in turn, makes the issue of increasing the survival rate of new businesses particularly relevant [14].

In January-December 2025, the gross regional product of Khorezm region amounted to 62,987.5 billion UZS, with a growth rate of 107.9 percent. In the structure of GRP, the services sector accounted for 26,309.4 billion UZS, agriculture, forestry, and fisheries for 20,190.5 billion UZS, industry for 9,487.6 billion UZS, construction for 5,871.4 billion UZS, and net taxes on products for 1,128.6 billion UZS. The share of small entrepreneurship in the region's GRP was 71.6 percent, which indicates the very high potential of small business in the regional economy (Table 1) [15] [16].

Table 1. Sectoral Structure of GRP and Employment Opportunities through Small Business in Khorezm Region¹ (2025)

Sector	Volume, billion UZS	Share, %	Opportunity to increase employment through small business
Services sector	26,309.4	41.8	Creation of rapid jobs through tourism, trade, catering, transport, household and digital services.
Agriculture, forestry, and fisheries	20,190.5	32.1	Creation of additional employment through agro-processing, packaging, storage, greenhouses, and cooperation.
Industry	9,487.6	15.1	Formation of sustainable jobs through small-scale production, sewing, construction materials, and processing of local raw materials.
Construction	5,871.4	9.3	Expansion of employment among small contractors, repair-service providers, and handicraft masters.
Net taxes on products	1,128.6	1.8	Has an indirect economic effect; direct job-creation potential is limited.

The table data show that the greatest economic opportunities for developing small business in Khorezm region are associated with the services sector and agriculture. The fact that the services sector accounts for 41.8 percent of GRP creates an opportunity for rapid employment through tourism, public catering, transport, trade, handicrafts, digital services, and household services. The high share of agriculture provides a basis for developing agro-processing, packaging, storage, logistics, and local branded products (Figure 1).

1 Note: Compiled by the author based on data from the Integrated Statistical Information System (SIAT) of the National Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the 2025 GRP press release.

Figure 1. Dynamics of Employment in Small Entrepreneurship in Khorezm Region² (2018-2024)

The figure shows that employment in small entrepreneurship entities in Khorezm region gradually recovered in the post-pandemic period. After the decline in 2020, growth was observed in 2021-2024, and in 2024 the number of employed people reached 621.0 thousand. However, the changes in the number of active small business entities occurred faster than employment growth, meaning that the employment capacity per entity did not increase sufficiently.

Based on the results of the study, the main opportunity for increasing employment through small business in Khorezm region can be expressed as follows: although small business entities play a leading role in ensuring employment, their potential can be further directed toward creating high-value-added, formal, sustainable, and profitable jobs [17].

This opportunity is supported by several factors. First, a certain part of small business is concentrated in trade and simple service activities; these segments provide numerous jobs and create a foundation for further increases in profitability and growth potential. Second, sectors with high employment capacity, such as agro-processing, tourism services, logistics, small-scale production, and digital services, offer broad prospects for expansion. Third, the ongoing development of monitoring, consulting, and market-access systems contributes to strengthening the sustainability of newly established entities. Fourth, women's and youth entrepreneurship is becoming increasingly integrated with employment policy [18].

As the first solution, it is advisable to introduce a regional "small business-employment chain" model in Khorezm region. This model combines the processes of financing small business, training, providing infrastructure, and ensuring market access into a single chain. Within the model, three to four priority areas with high employment capacity are identified in each district and city. For example, tourism services may be prioritized in Khiva city and Khiva district; trade-logistics and digital services in Urgench city; industry and agro-processing in Hazorasp and Tuproqqal'a; and storage and processing of agricultural products in Gurlan, Shovot, and Qo'shko'pir districts.

The second solution is to link financial support with the result of creating formal jobs. When allocating concessional loans or subsidies, along with the business plan, criteria such as the number of formal jobs to be created, the employment of workers on the basis of labor contracts, the enterprise's obligation to operate for at least 24 months, and tax revenues should be taken into account. This ensures that credit resources serve not only to open enterprises, but also to create real and sustainable employment.

The third solution is to introduce a 24-month "business monitoring and support" system for newly established small business entities. The first two years are the most vulnerable period for a business, and it is precisely at this stage that entrepreneurs need practical assistance in accounting, taxation, marketing, digital trade, product packaging, branding, and market entry. This approach is also consistent with the conclusions of Haltiwanger

2 Note: Compiled by the author based on SIAT data.

and co-authors regarding the special importance of young firms in job creation.

The fourth solution is to link the opportunities of the services sector and tourism with employment policy. The historical and cultural heritage of Khorezm region, the Khiva tourism center, handicrafts, guest houses, national cuisine, guiding services, and transport services make it possible to form a large number of small business entities. A special program combining microgrants, family business, digital booking, online sales, and multilingual marketing skills should be developed in this area.

The fifth solution is to support women's and youth entrepreneurship on the basis of the "training-financing-market access" chain. In this system, after short-term training courses, an entrepreneur receives a loan or subsidy and is then provided with mentoring, marketing, and access to sales channels for 6-12 months. Especially for women, childcare services, home-based production, online sales, handicrafts, and food processing can become effective sources of employment.

The sixth solution is to integrate small business entities into cooperative relations with large enterprises, farms, tourism facilities, and service networks. For example, a small enterprise may supply food products to guest houses, process agricultural products, provide small contracting services to construction organizations, or connect local handicraft products with the tourism market. This approach transforms small business from an isolated activity into part of an economic value chain.

Conclusions and suggestions

The development of small business entities in Khorezm region is one of the important economic opportunities for increasing employment. The statistical analysis shows that, although employment in small entrepreneurship entities fluctuated in 2018-2024, the overall trend was positive: in 2024 this indicator reached 621.0 thousand people. At the same time, the decline in the unemployment rate in the region is also associated with entrepreneurial activity and positive shifts in the labor market.

Furthermore, strengthening the impact of small business on employment can be achieved through the continued expansion of business entities. The main priority is to further enhance the employment capacity, survival rate, ability to create formal jobs, and integration of small business into high-value-added sectors. For Khorezm region, the services sector, tourism, agro-processing, logistics, handicrafts, small-scale production, and digital services are among the most promising and rapidly developing areas.

The main scientific proposal advanced in the article is the need to introduce the "small business-employment chain" model in Khorezm region. This model is based on selecting priority sectors by district, linking financing with the creation of formal jobs, monitoring new businesses for 24 months, bringing women's and youth entrepreneurship to the market, and integrating small business into local economic chains. This approach makes it possible to transform small business not only into a source of employment, but also into a sustainable factor of regional economic growth.

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